

Collaborative Governance in Managing Transportation Online

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Abstract

The progress of the digital era now has a very broad impact in all fields, at every level of society, not least in the field of transportation.

Transportation is a basic need for public access in all activities. The development of transportation is progressing rapidly with online transportation, both cars and motorbikes, making it easy for the public to access this mode of online transportation and is also cheaper than conventional transportation. However, the development of uncontrolled online transportation will cause several problems and horizontal conflicts with conventional transportation.

Agencies or companies engaged in the transportation sector today are considered to be very vulnerable to the development of issues that occur in the community. Especially with the advancement of information technology through mass media and social media, now it is not uncommon for this issue to end up with a negative perspective due to the distortion of communication in the community.

The purpose of this study is to analyze collaborative governance that has been implemented by the government to overcome transportation problems, especially between online and regular. The government needs to collaborate between stakeholders in the administration of government as an effort and the government's response in handling public problems. Collaborative governance is a collaboration between stakeholders involving the government, the private sector, and the community and is one of the solutions in solving the problem of Public Transportation. The research method uses a qualitative approach.

Key words: collaborative, governance, transportation, management, online

INTRODUCTION

The increase in the number of motorized vehicles is certainly in line with the increase in traffic congestion in Indonesia, especially in big cities. So as to be able to support the high mobility of the community, an effective mode of transportation is needed to be able to avoid or reduce congestion. Urban transportation problems generally include traffic congestion, parking, public transportation, pollution and traffic order problems (Munawar, 2007). Transportation problems, traffic jams, parking problems, public transportation, pollution, and traffic order problems are a series of urban transportation problems that are commonly faced by many big cities in the world, including in Indonesia. This problem must be addressed immediately because the purpose of urban transportation is to revive the city, if the transportation system runs well.

Another problem that is not less important is public transport facilities. Urban public transportation, which is currently dominated by bus and microbus transportation, still feels uncomfortable, less secure and less efficient. Mass rapid transit such as trains is still not functioning enough for urban public transportation. Jostling in public transportation is a daily view in big cities. Users of public transport services are still limited to the lower classes and some of the middle class. (Ayu Aziah, Popon Rabia Adawia: 2018)

The presence of online transportation that prioritizes the use of technology for human convenience is in fact not always seen positively by all parties. Conventional transportation industry players are directly affected because their income has declined sharply after the emergence of online application-based transportation. Online transportation arises amid the conditions of the transportation system in Indonesia that have not been well ordered. Online transportation offers convenience, lower costs, more convenience and security, so it is not surprising that many people are switching from conventional modes of transportation to online modes of transportation. Over time, the presence of online transportation has caused social jealousy for conventional transportation that has been there before, both motorcycle taxis, taxis, buses and so on. (<https://journal.uny.ac.id/index.php/informasi/article/view/9657/7704>)

Therefore the Government must make a breakthrough and cooperation with other parties, both private and public. Collaborative Governance is a solution for the government in overcoming the problems

of urban transportation in order to increase community economic access. Collaboration is defined as a form of cooperation, interaction, compromise of several elements related either individuals, institutions or parties involved directly and indirectly who receive the consequences and benefits (Haryono, N., 2012: 48) The explanation emphasizes that various forms of work Similarly, interactions in government, as well as conflict resolution in various actors involved directly or indirectly will receive the effects of governance.

The impact of governance can be optimized through planning. One country that uses a collaborative approach is Indonesia. The main problems of developing countries such as Indonesia, especially in urban areas are traffic jams, slums, the need for clean water, and the need for healthy air. Hafis, Hakim, and Haryono added that besides these problems, the global community is currently also facing problems, one of which is related to transportation. Therefore this research is important to do, where this research wants to analyze the factors that influence online Transportation Governance in the context of collaborative governance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Collaborative Governance in managing Transportation Based Online

Ansell and Gash explained that the new strategy of governance is called collaborative governance. The form of governance that involves various stakeholders or stakeholders together in a forum with government officials to make joint decisions. (Ansell and Alison, 2007: 543). O'Flynn and Wanna define collaboration as working together or working together with others. This implies that an actor or an individual, group or organization cooperates in several businesses. Every person who cooperates with others has certain terms and conditions, where it varies greatly. The word "collaboration" was originally used in the nineteenth century in the development of industrialization, the emergence of more complex organizations, and the increasing division of labor and tasks. These conditions constitute the basic norms of utilitarianism, social liberalism, collectivism, mutual assistance and the management of scientific and organizational theories of human relations. (O'Flynn and John, 2008: 3)

Donahue and Zeckhauser interpreted "collaborative governance can be thought of a form of agency relationship between government as principal, and private players as agent." (Donahue and Richard, 2011: 30) Referring to the various understandings explained about collaborative governance, it can be explained that basically the need for collaboration arises from the interdependence relationships that exist between parties or between stakeholders. Collaborative governance can be explained as a process that involves shared norms and mutually beneficial interactions between governance actors. From the perspective of collaborative governance, positive goals from each party can be achieved. Factors that Influence Collaborative Governance Success according to Goldsmith and Kettl are: that there are important things that can be used as criteria for the success of a network or collaboration in governance, namely: Networked Structure, Commitment to a Common Purpose, Trust Among the Participants, Governance, Access to Authority , Distributive Accountability / Responsibility, Information Sharing, Access to Resources. (Goldsmith and Donald, 2009: 135-136).

Online Transportation Phenomenon, in the perspective of good governance

Traffic congestion, parking problems, public transportation, and traffic order issues are a series of urban transportation problems that are commonly faced by many big cities in the world, including in Indonesia. This problem must be addressed immediately because the purpose of urban transportation is to revive the city, if the transportation system runs well. We can examine the phenomenon of online transportation in Indonesia from different perspectives, namely consumer behavior of Indonesian people and good governance. Human life develops rapidly from time to time. The presence of technology without us can avoid being able to change the face of the world and make the world seem without limits. So that the Indonesian people in general have placed online transportation as a common transportation method. This has happened in such a way because there have been major changes to the habits and behavior of Indonesian people. The main factor underlying the change is the presence of smartphone technology. The penetration of digital technology in the form of smartphones in Indonesia is extraordinary. Based on data compiled by emarketer survey agencies, it is stated that Indonesia is one of the third largest smartphone users in the Asia Pacific after China and India. In fact, the number of active smartphones used in Indonesia is approximately 208 million units, exceeding Indonesia's population of 200 million. In addition, smartphones for modern society are no exception for Indonesian people who are like clothes that keep clinging all day long.

This change in behavior in modern society has been captured by online transportation application companies such as Go-Jek, Grab, and Uber. How changes in people's behavior are affected by the presence of smartphone technology is associated with transportation needs where there are still so wide gaps that have not been tackled by conventional transportation. By providing added value to consumers, online transportation offers a smartphone-based application service to fulfill not only transportation but also delivery services, food delivery services and other services quickly and at relatively affordable prices. Because the presence of online transportation is able to be a solution in the midst of modern society that is close to technology, the development of online transportation is growing rapidly and is able to shake the stability of conventional transportation.

(<https://www.perbanas.ac.id/id/component/k2/item/689-fenomena-transportation-online-a-perspective-behavior-consumer>)

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative content analysis method. Qualitative content analysis, according to Bibber & Leavy (2005, p. 1278) is "a research method for subjective interpretation of text content data through a process of classification and identification of themes or systematic patterns." This qualitative content analysis is systematic, analytical but not as rigid as content analysis quantitative. Categorization is only used as a guide, allowing other concepts or categories to emerge during the research process. In this study, the unit of analysis is a reference, a series of words or sentences that indicate something that has meaning in accordance with the categories of collaborative governance and online transportation. Researchers collect news related to online transportation and analyze cooperation or collaboration between government, private parties and the community related to online transportation. Content analysis is carried out on electronic, print and online media.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the context of the 21st century, (Amajida, 2016) said that technology has driven the development of digital society. People can now be connected to the internet all the time and digital devices are connected to the internet in almost all locations. Smartphones and tablet computers can be easily carried all the time. In addition to using internet access as a backbone, the Android-based ojek transportation mode also uses GPS as a support service. GPS provides benefits in terms of navigation and placement (Amajida, 2016). The use of GPS features as a form of technology provides an opportunity to obtain certainty regarding distance, time and direction. The GPS feature used in the motorcycle taxi mode is able to track the whereabouts of the fleet, so users can get the opportunity to get certainty in terms of distance and time.

Starting with the presence of the company PT Go-Jek Indonesia in 2011 which was founded by Nadiem. Nadiem created Go-Jek, a pick-up, modern motorcycle taxi service. Motorcycle taxi which is a two-wheeled motor vehicle has become a very effective transportation. This application allows users to order motorcycle taxi online. Gojek is known as a modern and professional motorcycle taxi. The drivers have been equipped with android-based mobile phones with the aim of making it easier for drivers to connect with users and can easily get the best route for carrying passengers (Aziah, A., & Rabia, P.: 2018).

The presence of online transportation services has certainly drawn a lot of controversy, at the beginning of 2016, thousands of public transport drivers who felt their income was declining due to the presence of online transportation services finally held a demonstration. This incident did not only take place once, they returned to the demonstration a week later. This also forced the government to immediately take a stand. The government also had to require drivers of online transportation vehicles to change the name on the Vehicle Number Certificate (STNK) into the name of the company or cooperative.

At the end of 2016, conflicts emerged from online motorcycle taxi companies themselves such as GO-JEK who were pressured by their own drivers who felt their incomes were too small. Uniquely, towards the end of 2016, taxi companies which previously seemed to oppose online transportation services, actually changed their attitude. They finally looked at online transportation services as an opportunity, and established cooperation with them. This is shown by the collaboration between Blue Bird and GO-JEK. So we can order a fleet of taxiBlue Bird through the GO-JEK application.

Picture 1
Data of Online Transportation Application Users in Indonesia

Source: Data processed 2019

In addition to the three startup companies mentioned above there are similar local companies as previously described namely Blue-Jek, Lady-Jek, Top-Jek, Ojek Syar-I, but due to competition and capital many of these brands are no longer in operation. In 2019 the rules for online motorcycle taxis finally appeared. With this legal umbrella, online ojek has a foundation to operate. That rule is Minister of Transportation Regulation No. 12 of 2019 concerning Safety Protection of Motorcycle Users which is used for the Interest of the Community. Director General of Transportation of the Ministry of Transportation, Budi Setyadi, said that this regulation is related to motorcycle safety protection issues that are used for the benefit of the public, or online motorcycle taxi regulations.

Furthermore, this rule itself is expected to accommodate the interests of a number of parties, from drivers, applicators, to consumers. Then, the regulated aspects include safety, partnerships, suspensions, and service fees. The new online taxi rules are in Indonesia and have been enacted since June 18, 2019. This new online taxi rule replaces the previous regulation that was revoked by the Supreme Court (MA), namely Regulation of the Minister of Transportation No. 108 of 2017 concerning the Implementation of Transportation of People with Public Motor Vehicles Not in Route. The decision to revoke the PM 108 was due to the abolition of the article, among others in the form of regulating special markings in the form of stickers placed on vehicle windshield containing certain information and rules on KIR test questions which were also canceled.

The following are the new rules for online taxation Ministerial Regulation 118, which have been quoted from official pages owned by the Department of Transportation or the Ministry of Transportation, including

1. Car Capacity

For organizers and online taxi drivers, of course, they must ensure that four-wheeled vehicles or cars are used according to the new rules in force. In this regulation, questioning a car must have a cylinder capacity of at least 1,000 cc.

2. Operational Area

The online taxi operating area is also specified in the new rules, including within the urban area, from and to the airport, port or other transportation node.

3. Car License Plate

Although both carry passengers, online taxis and ordinary taxis have differences in their cars. If the taxi plates are generally yellow, but online taxis are the same as private cars in general, namely the basic black color with white writing.

4. Having an Indonesian Legal Entity

Every business or business that runs must of course have an Indonesian legal entity, this is the same for all online taxi operators.

5. Monitoring Equipment

Online taxi operators need to prepare a monitoring device that is installed in each of their partner cars for direct monitoring of the work of the driver from recording the vehicle's speed to the driver's behavior.

6. Upper and Lower Limit Rates

Do not just charge a trip if you do not want to be penalized. The organizer must pay close attention to the matter of the upper and lower limit rates.

7. Transportation Rates

Online taxi transportation rates under this new rule will consist of indirect and direct costs. This tariff is not determined by the respective organizers, but has been determined directly by the Minister. In addition, the tariff provisions must also be listed on the application, so that online taxi passengers can see it directly.

8. Quota Limits

Online taxi operators do not limit someone who wants to be their partner, both young and old can become online taxi drivers according to criteria.

9. Suspend Criteria

As a form of protection for consumers or taxi passengers online to feel safe and comfortable, requires the online taxi operators to have criteria regarding the deactivation or sanctions given to the driver's partner if a violation is made.

10. Digital Dashboard Access

Every online taxi organizer must also give Minister or Governor Digital Dashboard access.

However, if a violation of the new regulation is found, then there is a sanction prepared by the DoT for violators of the regulation, including 3 warnings that are applied in stages, such as: Warning 1 like SP 1 or mild, Warning 2 like SP 2 or medium, Warning 3 such as SP 3 or weight.

CONCLUSION

In the current era of technology which is increasingly rapid, almost in all fields is no exception in the field of transportation. With the increase in the number of motorized vehicles, of course, it will also increase congestion in Indonesia, especially in big cities. So as to be able to support the high mobility of the community, an effective mode of transportation is needed to be able to avoid or reduce congestion.

To answer the needs of the community, several companies providing online transportation applications have been born. Online transportation arises amid the conditions of the transportation system in Indonesia that have not been well ordered. Several large companies are competing to form an online application-based transportation company. The government together with the private sector has collaborated in the field of online transportation, this collaboration is strengthened by the Minister of Transportation Regulation No. 12 of 2019 concerning Safety Protection for Motorcycle Users which is used for the Interest of the Community. Director General of Transportation of the Ministry of Transportation, Budi Setyadi, said that this regulation is related to motorcycle safety protection issues that are used for the benefit of the community, or regulations for online motorcycle taxis..

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